

Course Portfolio on Algorithmics (Apprenticeship)

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Abstract

This portfolio documents the teaching and delivery of the COMP-SCI2026 Algorithmics course at the University of Glasgow during the academic year 2022-2023. As part of the Disciplinary Commons in Theoretical Computer Science (Algorithms Education) project, it provides a reflective account of the course structure, pedagogical approaches, assessment strategies, and student engagement techniques. The course, designed for second-year students in the Graduate Apprenticeship in Software Engineering programme, a BSc undergraduate degree, aims to develop algorithmic problem-solving skills through theoretical foundations and practical applications. Key topics include fundamental algorithms, NP-completeness, and computability. The document also discusses innovations in teaching methods, such as pair programming for algorithm tracing, and explores challenges associated with block-mode teaching. The portfolio offers insights into the evolving pedagogical strategies for algorithm education and contributes to the broader discourse on computing science pedagogy.

Overview

COMPSCI2026 Algorithmics course is a core second-year course on the Graduate Apprenticeship in Software Engineering programme (hereinafter referred to as **GA**) - a 4-year BSc (Honours) in Software Engineering degree at the School of Computing Science, University of Glasgow, UK. The academic level is SCQF Level 8 in Scotland, which is equivalent¹ to RQF&CQFW Level 5 in England/Wales, and EQF Level 5 in the European Qualification Framework.

¹Comparison between qualification levels on the Scottish Credit and Qualifications Framework (SCQF), the Regulated Qualifications Framework (RQF) and Credit and Qualifications Framework (CQFW) in England and Wales, and the European Qualifications Framework (EQF). <https://www.sqa.org.uk/sqa/64561.html>

1 Context

1.1 Degree Programme Context

The GA programme was launched in autumn 2019 to accommodate a diverse range of learners, including school leavers, individuals seeking a career change, and existing employees aiming to transition into a Software Engineering role. Each yearly cohort of the GA programme comprises between 20 and 45 students, employed across a variety of organisations in Scotland, including prominent names such as Barclays, Morgan Stanley, and the BBC, public sector bodies like the Scottish Qualifications Authority (SQA) and Public Health Scotland, and innovative tech start-ups such as VeryConnect.

The GA programme is structured differently from other degree offerings. With a strong emphasis on work-based learning, students spend the majority of their time in the workplace, complemented by brief, intensive teaching sessions on campus. The work/study ratio is approximately 80/20. Teaching is front-loaded with workplace-relevant skills to enable apprentices to quickly contribute as effective team members.

For Levels 1 and 2, each semester in an academic session spans eight consecutive weeks. During these semesters, students attend 2 x 2-hour contact sessions per day, Monday-Friday during odd-numbered weeks, and Monday to Wednesday during even-numbered weeks. Semester 1 begins in late October with the exam diet in early February. Semester 2 starts in early March with the exam diet in May. Courses worth 20 credits run for the whole eight weeks, while 10-credit courses run for four weeks. Work-based assessment courses are typically year-long and carry 20 credits in Level 1 and 40 credits in Level 2.

This degree was developed by the Centre for Computing Science Education at the University of Glasgow, following extensive consultation with over 20 employers to ensure alignment with industry needs. The design also draws on extensive international research on best practice in work-based learning. The structure of the programme is as follows:

Year 1: In the first teaching block, students acquire skills and tools that enable them to quickly adapt to the primary programming languages used in the workplaces, alongside learning the fundamentals of professional software development. The second block focuses on testing fundamentals and web application development courses, equipping students with the tools to improve existing software systems.

Year 2: Students learn about data storage, data science, systems, human-computer interaction, fundamental algorithmic content to broaden their understanding of the wider computing field, and further concepts and tools related to professional software engineering.

Years 3 and 4: Half of the credits are earned through Honours or Masters-level elective courses offered to students on the traditional Software Engineering BSc (Hons). The remaining credits are awarded through long-term

workplace projects and assignments, collaboratively defined by students, employers, and academic supervisors.

The School of Computing Science, University of Glasgow, offers the following undergraduate degrees programmes, with BSc 4-years long and MSci (or integrated Masters) 5-years long:

- Computing Science [BSc/MA/MA(SocSci)/MSci],
- Electronic & Software Engineering [BSc/BEng/MEng],
- Software Engineering [BSc/MSci], and
- Software Engineering Graduate Apprenticeship [BSc].

as well as some other programs in partnership with overseas HE institutions.

The minimum entry requirements for the Software Engineering Graduate Apprenticeship (GA) are slightly less stringent than those for the Software Engineering [BSc/MSci] degree and Computing Science [BSc/MSci]. Applicants must have achieved at least a grade B in Higher Mathematics and two Science subjects at Higher level. GA students come from diverse mathematical backgrounds and, unlike their peers in traditional undergraduate programmes, are not enrolled in Mathematics courses during Level 1 or Level 2. To address this, a non-credit-bearing course on basic Mathematics is provided to incoming Level 1 GA students prior to the start of Semester 1.

1.2 Place within the GA Programme

Pre-requisites courses. COMPSCI2026 is a 10-credit core course delivered during the first four weeks of Semester 2 in Year 2. It builds upon the Year 2 Semester 1 GA course COMPSCI1021 Practical Algorithms (20 credits), which introduces students to a wide range of basic data structures and algorithm and discrete mathematics. This foundation equips students with essential mathematical concepts in computing, facilitating a deeper understanding of efficient programming and serving as a basis for more advanced mathematical topics in subsequent courses.

To succeed in COMPSCI2026, students must possess Java programming skills, as Java-like pseudocode or Java code is used extensively to present algorithms and forms a key component of the assessed coursework. Students are expected to develop Java proficiency through the Year 1 30-credit course, COMPSCI1020 How to Learn a New Language. However, while some students are proficient in Java, others may primarily be familiar with Python, which is the focus of Year 1 teaching and used exclusively in COMPSCI1021 Practical Algorithms. Progression to Level 2 is guaranteed for students who achieve a GPA of D3 or better in their Level 1 courses at the first attempt. Consequently, all students enrolled in COMPSCI2026 will have attained at least a D3 grade in COMPSCI1020, ensuring a baseline familiarity with Java programming.

Pre-requisite role. For students continuing to Honours-level study, COMPSCI2026 serves as a pre-requisite, as it is equivalent to the core Honours COMPSCI4009 Algorithmics I, for the Honours-level courses such as COMPSCI4003 *Algorithmics II (H)* and COMPSCI5116 *Computational Game Theory (M)*. However, the introduction to computability section could serve as a requirement for the Honours-level course COMPSCI4031 *Modelling Reactive Systems (H)*, but not formally specified at the moment.

1.3 Curriculum Design Context

The course specification for COMPSCI2026 was originally designed by a group of academic in the Centre for Computing Science Education as part of the GA programme. The content and assessment were adapted from the compulsory undergraduate Level 3 Honours Semester 1 course COMPSCI4009 Algorithmics I. While COMPSCI4009 is set at SCQF Level 10 (Scottish Credit and Qualifications Framework), COMPSCI2026 is delivered at SCQF Level 8. The curriculum for COMPSCI2026 was developed using a top-down approach, with only minor adjustments made to align the content with the lower academic level. These adjustments primarily involved the removal of a small number of advanced topics and tutorial exercises that were designated as non-examinable or particularly challenging.

1.4 Lecturer Context

I have served as the sole course coordinator and lecturer for COMPSCI2026 since the inception of the programme. My expertise stems from over 20 years of experience as a researcher in theoretical computer science, particularly in the area of formal methods.

My academic career began in 2004 as a tenured teaching assistant in the Faculty of Informatics at the "Al.I.Cuza" University of Iași, Romania. During this time, I was simultaneously enrolled in an MSc programme in Distributed Systems and conducted research in formal methods. From 2005 to 2008, I pursued a PhD at INRIA Nancy, France, focusing on term and graph rewriting calculi. In 2009, I joined the School of Computing Science at the University of Glasgow as a postdoctoral researcher, contributing to several research projects and programme grants in the domain of formal modelling and verification until 2020.

I began my current role as a Lecturer on the Learning, Teaching, and Scholarship (LTS) track in the School of Computing Science in September 2020. I am a member of the *Education and Practice (EAP)* research section and affiliated with the *Formal Analysis, Theory and Algorithms (FATA)* research section. Given that the topics covered in COMPSCI2026 align closely with theoretical computer science, my academic background made it a natural fit for me to coordinate and teach this course.

As an LTS Lecturer, I am expected to demonstrate a strong commitment to enhancing student learning and achieving significant accomplishments as an

educator. This includes advancing pedagogy in Higher Education, influencing policy and practice within the educational sector, motivating colleagues, and leading activities that benefit staff and students while supporting the University's educational mission.

Between 2021 and 2023, I completed the Postgraduate Certificate in Academic Practice (PGCAP), a 60-credit SCQF Level 11 programme, which recognized me as a RET Fellow. RET (Recognizing Excellence in Teaching) is the University of Glasgow's internal CPD framework designed to provide professional development opportunities and recognition of expertise in teaching and learning, aligned with the AdvanceHE Professional Standards Framework (2011). Building on this foundation, I am currently pursuing the MEd in Academic Practice, with graduation anticipated in 2025.

In addition to my role as the sole instructor responsible for delivering all lectures, one or two Graduate Teaching Assistants (GTAs) typically assist with the tutorial and lab sessions. These GTAs are usually affiliated with the FATA research section.

1.5 Educational Research Output

In my Algorithmics course, I focus on advancing students' skills in designing and analysing algorithms, also covering essential topics such as NP-completeness, solvability, and computability. My educational research over the years has focused on refining pedagogical strategies to support students in understanding these complex topics, particularly through the lens of collaborative learning techniques like Pair Programming (PP). Through a series of studies, I have explored how PP enhances students' engagement and comprehension in both abstract topics, such as finite state automata, and algorithm tracing. For example, my work on using PP in algorithm tracing has shown that students benefit from collaborative problem-solving as it helps to manage cognitive load and deepen their understanding of algorithmic processes [1, 2]. Moreover, my investigation into integrating large language models (LLMs) as AI-assisted partners for algorithm tracing furthers this goal by addressing the challenges inherent in traditional pairings [3]. The synergy between these educational research inquiries and the course's objectives has led to iterative improvements in teaching strategies, fostering a deeper understanding of algorithmic concepts while also promoting active, collaborative learning environments.

2 Course Objectives and Content

2.1 Course Aims

The aim of this course is to further develop the student's skills in the design and analysis of algorithms. The students study algorithms for a range of important standard problems. They are also introduced to the theory of NP-completeness

and fundamental concepts of computability, together with their practical implications.

2.2 Intended Learning Outcomes

As per current proforma, by the end of this course students will be able to:

ILO1 *Apply* standard algorithmic design methods and basic principles of algorithm analysis.

ILO2 *Describe* fundamental graph and string algorithms and be able to *apply* this knowledge in a program.

ILO3 *Describe* the basic principles and practical implications of the theory of NP-completeness.

ILO4 *Provide* examples of the computability and unsolvability, and *know* some standard examples of unsolvable problems.

2.3 Background Concepts

In this section I give more details regarding pre-requisite concepts from courses mentioned in Section 1.2.

This course requires basic knowledge of Java that students acquired during the Year 1 course *How to Learn a New Language*. The algorithms in this course are presented either using the Java or a Java-style pseudocode. Some algorithms are partially or fully implemented in Java. The exercises for the practical sessions (laboratory) require Java as well as the coursework exercises.

The students are expected to know from the Year 2 Semester 2 course *Practical Algorithms* course the following: fundamental concepts of graphs, terminology and notation of sets, relations and functions, basic mathematical reasoning and proof, concept of an abstract data type, common data structures (e.g., lists, arrays and binary trees), basics of algorithm analysis (e.g., time complexity and big-O notation), common searching algorithms (e.g., linear search and binary search), common sorting algorithms (e.g., insertion sort and merge sort).

2.4 Syllabus

The syllabus for the course is organised in six units:

Unit 0: Quick recap on algorithm analysis: Big O notation, log function, polynomial time vs. exponential time - pre-lecture 1 as pre-recorded video

Unit 1: Sorting: comparison-based sorting, radix sorting, tries data structure - lecture 1

Unit 2: String and text algorithms: text compression (Huffman encoding, LZW compression/decompression), string comparison, string/pattern search (brute force algorithm, Knuth-Morris-Pratt algorithm, Boyer-Moore algorithm) - lectures 2, 3, and 4

Unit 3: Graphs and graph algorithms: graph search and traversal (depth first search, breadth first search), shortest path (Dijkstra’s algorithm), minimum spanning tree (Prim-Jarnik and Dijkstra’s refinement), topological ordering - lectures 5, 6, and 7

Unit 4: An introduction to NP-completeness: classes P and NP, classical NP-complete problems, polynomial-time reductions, proving a problem is NP-complete - lectures 8 and 9

Unit 5: A brief introduction to computability: the halting problem, models of computation (finite-state automata, pushdown automata, Turing Machines, counter machine, Church-Turing thesis) - lectures 10, 11, and 12

Timetable. The course is delivered in block-mode teaching over 4 consecutive weeks in March, consisting of 32 formal contact hours.

- Weeks 1 and 3: 2 hours each day Monday to Friday, scheduled flexibly (lectures, tutorials, and labs)
- Weeks 2 and 4: 2 hours each day Monday to Wednesday, scheduled flexibly (lectures and tutorials)

The usual daily delivery pattern is one hour lecture followed by one hour tutorial session. A total of 3-4 hours of lab sessions are set up starting from the end of week 1.

Attendance to all lectures, tutorials and lab session is mandatory as required by the employers. Attendance is recorded via a our VLE Moodle with daily passkey provided at the beginning of each daily session.

2.5 Textbooks

The following books are recommended but not required:

- (for units 0-3) M.T. Goodrich and R. Tamassia. *Algorithm Design: Foundations, Analysis, and Internet Examples*. Wiley, 2002. (Newer version available: *Algorithm Design and Applications*. Wiley, 2014)
- (for unit 4) D. Harel and Y. Feldman. *Algorithmics: the Spirit of Computing*. Springer, 2014.
- (for unit 5) M. Sipser. *Introduction to the Theory of Computation*. Thomson Course Technology, 2006.

3 Methods and Teaching Philosophy

The course materials are all inherited from the honours course COMPSCI4009.

Table 1 lists the learning and teaching methods alongside the time allocation for each category. Note that 100 notional learning hours correspond to 10 credits, i.e., 1 credit corresponds to 10 notional learning hours.

Table 1: Learning & Teaching Methods with Time Allocation

Learning and Teaching Method	Formal Contact Hours	National Learning Hours
Lecture	20.00	40.00
Tutorial	8.00	16.00
Practical classes	4.00	8.00
Work based learning	2.00	20.00
Guided independent study	Not applicable	20.00
Total	34.00	100.00

3.1 Lectures

Lectures serve as the primary medium for introducing the key concepts, definitions, and algorithms covered in the course. Students are not expected to complete any pre-reading before attending the lectures, aside from reviewing the recap slides and accompanying pre-recorded videos. This pre-lecture material has been designed to cover foundational concepts typically revisited in the first lecture, allowing more time during lectures to focus on new material and deeper discussions.

In Units 1–3, lectures typically cover an average of two algorithms per session, alongside a review of relevant data structures. Each algorithm is introduced with its motivation, followed by either Java code or Java-like pseudocode, a tracing example using sample input, and an analysis of its complexity. Based on student feedback from a previous academic session, I considered reversing the order by first tracing the algorithm on an example input and then presenting the pseudocode. While this approach can be effective in fostering intuition, I found it feasible only for specific algorithms, such as string-matching algorithms, where visualizing the process first can enhance understanding.

The lectures in the NP-completeness unit are content-heavy, focusing on formal definitions and the theoretical underpinnings of computational complexity. To balance this, I include numerous examples of NP-complete problems to provide context and improve student comprehension. Similarly, lectures on computability follow a structured format: motivation, formal definitions, and illustrative examples, ensuring that theoretical concepts are grounded in practical contexts.

3.2 Tutorials

For every lecture, I provide a corresponding tutorial sheet with exercises designed to reinforce the concepts introduced in class. Starting in the 2022–23 academic session, I enhanced these materials by including tracing exercises for all algorithms covered in the lectures. Previously, only about half of the algorithms had associated tracing exercises in the tutorials. This change ensures

that students consistently practice the critical skill of algorithm tracing, which is fundamental to their understanding of computational processes.

As part of my ongoing efforts to enhance student engagement and learning, I conducted a pilot inquiry into the use of pair programming for algorithm tracing. The study explored how collaborative learning could help students understand and apply algorithms more effectively. Insights from this pilot showed that students valued the collaborative nature of pair programming, particularly its role in clarifying complex algorithmic processes through peer discussion. Building on this positive feedback, I have integrated pair programming more extensively into tutorial sessions for algorithm tracing exercises. This approach not only fosters active learning but also strengthens problem-solving and teamwork skills, which are essential for both academic and professional success.

In tutorials, students attempt to solve exercises either independently or in pairs, as instructed. To support their learning, I dedicate time during each session to discuss model solutions to all tutorial exercises. These solutions are presented using PowerPoint slides, allowing for a structured review of key concepts and strategies while addressing common challenges faced by students. This iterative approach ensures that students can compare their solutions, ask questions, and clarify misunderstandings in a collaborative learning environment.

3.3 Practical Classes or Labs

Each year, I allocate 3–4 hours of lab sessions to support students in applying the theoretical concepts covered in the course. These sessions are facilitated with the assistance of one or two Graduate Teaching Assistants to ensure students receive adequate guidance and support.

The first lab session focuses on an exercise that involves implementing a data structure and its associated operations, serving as preparation for the assessed exercise. Students are provided with partially completed Java files containing incompletely specified methods. Their task is to complete these methods and test the program using given inputs. This hands-on activity helps reinforce their understanding of data structure implementation and debugging. At the end of the session, I provide model solutions and lead a discussion to highlight key approaches, common mistakes, and alternative solutions.

Subsequent lab sessions are dedicated to individual work on the assessed exercise. During these sessions, students are encouraged to ask questions and seek clarification on any aspects of the task. This focused environment allows them to progress at their own pace while receiving targeted support to overcome specific challenges.

3.4 Sample Learning Activities in Tutorials and Labs

3.4.1 Algorithm tracing exercises (ILOs 1-2)

This activity involves providing an input for an algorithm discussed during lectures and running it step-by-step through the algorithm. For each algorithm,

the instructor demonstrates an example trace during the lecture, followed by a tracing exercise assigned to students at the beginning of the tutorial session. Students are encouraged to work in pairs, adhering to the principles of pair programming. They bring prior experience of working in pairs from the *Practical Algorithms* course conducted in the previous semester, as well as exposure to pair programming from the Level 1 course, *Foundations of Professional Software Engineering*.

The pair programming for tracing algorithms activity was implemented and used in March 2023 during 7 tutorial sessions. Based on the study conducted during the course [2], the pilot investigation on using pair programming for algorithm tracing revealed that students generally valued the collaborative aspect of the activity, as it helped deepen their understanding of algorithms. However, the study also highlighted areas for improvement, such as enhancing the session structure and providing additional resources to address concerns about insufficient support and time constraints.

Example of tutorial exercise: Find the distance between the strings $s = agcgatc$ and $t = ctacgaccg$ by drawing the complete table filled in based on the recurrence relation defined in Lecture 3, and then derive an optimum alignment.

3.4.2 Coding fundamental string or graph algorithms (ILOs 2-3)

This lab activity requires students to take pseudocode or fragments of Java code and expand them into a full implementation of a given algorithm. Students work individually on their laptops, engaging in discussions with peers and seeking assistance from the lecturer or tutors when needed. The lecturer highlights potentially challenging aspects of the implementation and facilitated discussions on suitable data structures for the task.

Example of lab exercise: Extend the `Trie` class given in the lecture to incorporate a method that generates a list of all of the words represented in the trie. This extended class will then be used in a program that accepts as input a text file, and produces a list of all of the words occurring in it. Task: add a new method `extract` to the `Trie` class which traverses the trie and both extracts and returns a list of all of the distinct words represented in the trie.

3.4.3 "Live" automata and Turing Machine construction (ILO 5)

This activity involves the lecturer initiating the construction of a deterministic finite-state automaton, pushdown automaton, or Turing Machine for a given language description. The process demonstrates how to approach a solution, including intentionally or unintentionally introducing mistakes, and soliciting suggestions from students to complete the solution.

Example exercises:

1. Give a deterministic finite-state automaton for the language of all strings over a, b that contain at least three occurrences of a .
2. Design a Turing Machine which recognises the following language $L = \{a^n b^n c^n \mid n \geq 0\}$ where $S = \{a, b, c\}$. More precisely, the machine that will accept precisely those strings that consist of a number of consecutive a 's followed by the same number of consecutive b 's followed by the same number of consecutive c 's.

3.4.4 Small group collaborative learning (pair programming) for constructing automata (ILO 5)

This collaborative learning approach involves students working in pairs to solve an automata construction task. Given a language defined over an alphabet of two or three characters, students are tasked with constructing either a deterministic finite-state automaton or a pushdown automaton that recognizes the language. Within each pair, one student assumes the role of the driver, responsible for drawing the automaton, while the other acts as the pilot, overseeing the construction of states and transitions. For the second exercise, the roles are switched to ensure balanced participation. After the allocated time for completing the two tasks, a selection of individual solutions is discussed collectively at the front of the class.

A pilot of this collaborative learning activity for constructing automata was conducted during the 2021–2022 academic session but was not repeated in 2022–2023 due to time constraints. The pilot study [1] indicated that students found the activity engaging and beneficial, particularly in helping them collaboratively build their understanding of finite state automata. Based on this positive feedback, I plan to reintroduce the activity in the future and conduct an educational enquiry to systematically evaluate its impact on student learning.

3.5 Guided Independent Study

Guided independent study is an essential component of the course, designed to help students consolidate their understanding and deepen their knowledge of the material covered in lectures and tutorials. The following activities are recommended:

- Tracing algorithms with their own example inputs: Students are encouraged to go beyond the provided examples by selecting or designing their own inputs for algorithms discussed in the course. This practice helps develop a deeper understanding of the algorithm's mechanics and edge cases, enabling them to better internalize the logic and execution flow.
- Engaging with recommended supplementary material: On the course Moodle page, I provide links to additional resources, including articles, videos, and tutorials, that are relevant to the algorithms and concepts covered in

class. While these materials are not required for assessments or examinations, they offer valuable insights and alternative explanations that can enhance students' learning.

- **Completing tutorial exercises:** Students are encouraged to revisit and complete any unfinished exercises from the tutorial sessions. This allows them to reinforce their understanding of key concepts and techniques while also practising problem-solving independently or in study groups.
- **Working on assessed coding exercises:** Assessed exercises form a critical part of the course, requiring students to implement and test algorithms through coding. By dedicating time to these tasks, students not only prepare for evaluations but also build practical programming skills essential for their future careers.

4 Assessment and Feedback

As with lectures, tutorials, and labs, the assessment design for this course draws heavily on the template and materials from the Honours-level course COMP-SCI4009 *Algorithmics I*. To reduce the weight of a high-stakes final exam, I introduced an additional class test, which corresponds to an exam-style question. This serves both as practice for the final exam and as an opportunity for earlier feedback.

4.1 Summative Assessment

The summative assessment consists of four components, constructively aligned with the course's learning outcomes (LOs) and activities. These components include both formal and informal assessments, depending on whether they are conducted under controlled conditions.

Multiple-choice quizzes 5% (informal) At the end of each teaching week, a timed set of online, Moodle-based multiple-choice questions (MCQs) is released. These quizzes, containing 2–8 questions per set, cover all course content taught during the week and address LOs 1, 2, 4, and 5. The allowed time is proportional to the number of questions, with a maximum of 1 hour.

Feedback: Each question provides feedback on the answers, ensuring students receive immediate insights into their performance.

Class test 15% (formal) A timed written test covering topics from weeks 1 and 2 (comparison-based sorting, string, and graph algorithms) takes place at the start of week 3, after completing Unit 3. The class test addresses LOs 1, 2, and 3.

The test is individual, open-book, and conducted during the scheduled 2-hour contact session via Moodle. Students have 1.5 hours to complete the questions and an additional 30 minutes to submit their answers online.

Feedback: Students receive brief individual feedback on Moodle within three weeks, along with a general feedback report. This report highlights common mistakes, the marks lost for each error, and provides model solutions for review.

Assessed practical exercise 20% (informal) This take-home programming assignment covers topics from weeks 1 and 2, focusing on the design and implementation of string or graph algorithms. It is released during week 2, with a deadline at the end of week 5 or early in week 6. This component addresses LOs 1, 2, and 3.

Feedback: Individual feedback is provided on Moodle within three weeks, accompanied by general feedback summarizing common errors, how marks were allocated, and model solutions.

Written examination 60% (formal) This is a written timed exam taking place during the summer exam diet in May. It addresses ILOs 1 - 5. Sample exam papers are provided with model solutions during term time and revision sessions are held 1-2 weeks before the exam.

The exam paper consists of three questions, each with subquestions, in total 60 marks evenly split between the three questions.

The exam is an open books, online and on-campus setup, with all students in the same lab room, each accessing a lab computer for the exam paper and submission page both on Moodle. The students have 1h30 to answer the questions on paper and/or on the computer, plus an additional 30 minutes to submit their answers as a pdf file via Moodle.

The exam papers are vetted by a colleague in the School of Computing Science and then externally reviewed by an examiner from another institution. The exam scripts are marked by the course coordinator, with a sample of around six papers covering the whole range of awarded marks undergoing internal moderation. Marks are returned to the teaching office within two weeks.

Feedback. No individual feedback is provided, unless requested within a two weeks from releasing the marks. General feedback is provided to the class as well as model solutions, discussing general points for solutions, common mistakes observed in the exam scripts, marks lost for specific (common) errors, as well as how each question relates to LOs. The feedback is made available on the course's Moodle page within two weeks of the exam board's meeting.

Provisions for students with disabilities. Where needed, reasonable adjustments or alternative arrangements are put in place for students with declared disabilities. For example, for the class test and the final exam, such students will have additional 30 minutes allowed for each 30 minutes of the set exam time.

4.2 Formative Assessment

Formative assessment is an integral part of the course, designed to help students test and deepen their understanding of the material while receiving timely feedback to support their learning. The following activities and feedback mechanisms are included:

- **Tutorial work:** Weekly tutorial sessions provide exercises aligned with the concepts introduced in lectures. Students work either individually or collaboratively in small groups and are encouraged to seek help from the lecturer or tutor as needed. After completing the exercises, solutions are discussed in class, with the lecturer guiding the discussion to address common challenges and reinforce key concepts. Detailed model solutions are shared after each tutorial session, allowing students to review and reflect on their work.
- **Lab sessions:** Two 2-hour lab sessions are scheduled during the teaching block: one at the end of week 1 and the other at the start of week 3. These sessions focus on applying and implementing fundamental algorithms introduced in weeks 1 and 2. Students work individually or in groups on programming exercises, receiving on-the-spot assistance and feedback from the lecturer and tutor. During the second half of each session, the lecturer leads a class discussion to highlight key issues and features of the exercises. Model solutions are provided to consolidate understanding.
- **Assessed exercise preparation:** One of the lab exercises serves as a foundation for the assessed practical exercise (AE), helping students familiarise themselves with the problem-solving and implementation requirements. Students typically have 3 weeks to complete and submit their work. To support them, two 1-hour help sessions are scheduled in the weeks following the assessed exercise release, where the lecturer provides guidance and addresses individual questions.
- **Feedback on the assessed exercise submissions:** Individual feedback is provided through Moodle, complemented by general feedback in class and as a detailed document, which includes model solutions and explanations of common errors. This feedback directly supports students' mastery of ILOs 1–3, particularly in preparation for the first question of the final exam. Additionally, feedback from tutorial work and weekly quizzes reinforces the learning outcomes assessed in the exam.

Midway formative feedback for the lecturer. A Moodle questionnaire collects anonymous feedback from students midway through the course. This feedback covers learning methods, course content, and areas where students need additional support or clarification. The lecturer reviews this feedback and discusses the findings in class, making necessary adjustments to enhance the learning experience for the remaining weeks. This process also informs the emphasis placed on specific topics during the revision lecture.

Summative feedback mechanisms. At the end of the course, summative feedback is gathered through the institutional EvaSys platform. This feedback provides insights into the effectiveness of the course design and delivery, guiding future improvements.

4.3 Learning and Teaching Environment

During my first year teaching this course, I delivered it fully remotely with pre-recorded videos for lectures and online, synchronous tutorial and lab sessions. During the second year, the delivery was in person with a hybrid option (live via Zoom) for the students who were not able to attend in person. During the third year, in March 2023, I will be using technology-enabled active learning (TEAL) spaces at the University of Glasgow where students are seated around tables (maximum 7 occupancy), with several whiteboards and projector screens around the room.

The Virtual Learning Environment (VLE) used by the University of Glasgow is Moodle. The GA programme has a dedicated Moodle Workbook listing all courses and assessments for all GA cohorts and each GA course has its own Moodle page.

The lecture materials have been made available on the course's Moodle page, with pre-recorded videos available on Zoom. Moodle Multiple-Choice Questions quiz functionality has been used for weekly summative assessment (worth 5% of the final grade).

I have been using various digital media for asynchronous contact, communication and feedback:

- a Microsoft Teams dedicated channel, Moodle announcements, and email for non-anonymous questions and general communication,
- dedicated Padlet for anonymous comments and questions, and
- mid-term Moodle feedback (anonymous).

For synchronous, digital, anonymous communication and engagement in class I am using Mentimeter.

Most of the tools used in this course (Moodle, Zoom, Microsoft Teams, and Mentimeter) are supported by the University of Glasgow and hence do not pose any GDPR concerns. However, Padlet is not supported. Therefore, I will explicitly remind students to log out before accessing the Padlet in all our communications as well as on the Padlet page itself. All the tools for visualising or running algorithms are free to use and do not require an account, hence these pose no GDPR concerns.

Student expectations of the digital learning environment with respect to equitable access are generally fulfilled as each GA student is provided with a laptop at the start of Level 1, they have internet access while on campus every day or in their workplace, all essential course materials (lecture slideshows, videos, tutorial and lab sheets are downloadable and made available on the

institutional VLE Moodle in advance), the TEAL space used by the GA cohort is equipped with sufficient power sockets per table and also made available to them for the two hours between the two courses of each day on the campus.

5 Some Final Reflections

Lectures: moving toward student-focused learning. My current lecture style leans toward a teacher-centred approach, and I recognise the need to transition toward more student-focused methods to enhance engagement. One strategy to achieve this is incorporating short quizzes and polls using tools like Mentimeter. I have experimented with Mentimeter in one lecture, and it showed potential, but its consistent and meaningful integration requires careful planning. Each activity must be relevant, well-aligned with the lecture content, and designed to motivate students to actively participate. Additionally, I need to slow the lecture pace to ensure deeper understanding. Removing advanced, non-examinable content from lectures and making it available on Moodle as supplementary material may help manage the cognitive load and allow for a more deliberate teaching pace.

Block-mode teaching and cognitive load. Block-mode teaching presents unique challenges in managing cognitive load, especially with the intensive schedule. One potential improvement is balancing lecture and tutorial sessions more effectively. Should we schedule a lecture followed immediately by a tutorial on the same topic to reinforce learning, or alternate days of 2-hour lectures and tutorials/labs to give students time to process and apply the material? This is an area requiring reflection and potentially student feedback to identify the optimal schedule.

Labs: enhancing practical learning. Lab sessions are invaluable for applying theoretical knowledge, but there is room to improve their effectiveness. Introducing new exercises and expanding the number of lab sessions by one or two could help address gaps, especially for students struggling with Java. Allowing students the option to code in Python, a language many are more familiar with, might reduce barriers and boost confidence while maintaining focus on algorithmic problem-solving.

Teaching Theoretical Computer Science (TCS) topics. The TCS elements of the course, such as tracing algorithms, designing automata, and solving problems with Turing Machines, require a rigorous and structured approach. My aim is to continue providing detailed explanations and step-by-step solutions for these tasks to reinforce precision and logical reasoning. These methods not only build core skills but also contribute to a better understanding of the theoretical foundations of computer science.

Algorithmic Thinking vs. Computational Thinking. One of my goals is to foster algorithmic thinking, but I am reflecting on how it differs from computational thinking. Algorithmic thinking emphasises problem-solving through clear steps, logic, and efficiency, while computational thinking is broader, encompassing decomposition, abstraction, and generalization. Striking the right balance in teaching these skills is key to preparing students for both theoretical and practical challenges.

Real-world applications and engagement. To increase student engagement, I aim to make a stronger connection between course content and real-world problems. Highlighting applications of algorithms, exploring practical implications of NP-complete problems, and connecting automata and Turing Machines to real-world systems could help students see the relevance and importance of these topics.

Addressing high-stakes assessment. In the first year, the final exam contributed 80% of the final grade, similar to the Algorithmics I (H) course. To reduce this high-stakes burden, I introduced an in-class test to replace the assessed exercise. This adjustment aimed to distribute the weight more evenly and give students an opportunity for earlier feedback. While this change has been positive, there is still room to further improve the assessment strategy.

Collaborative assessment for engagement. To further address engagement, I am considering adding a collaborative assessment component, such as Moodle-based wikis (worth 10%). These wikis could involve students exploring real-world applications of algorithms, analysing NP-complete problems, or discussing automata and Turing Machines. To accommodate this, the in-class test could be removed (freeing up 2 hours of contact time), and 5% of the assessment could be allocated to class participation. This approach may enhance collaboration, critical thinking, and application of course concepts while reducing reliance on traditional assessment methods.

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